

2. Effect of subsurface water level on rainfed rice, Raipur, India.

was less susceptible to drought than Mahsuri. It had less leaf rolling and high root density.

Figure 2 shows the role of subsurface water in rainfed culture. The groundwater level fell during the

cropping season. Longer duration rices suffered more drought stress and yields declined. Subsoil moisture (30-80 cm deep) was particularly important to medium and late duration varieties in semiwet season (see table). *ℒ*

Effect of subsoil moisture on 6 rice genotypes, Raipur, India.

	Poorva	MW10	IR36	Usha	Safri 17	Mahsuri
<i>Grain yield^a (t/ha)</i>						
Wet	2.5	3.5	2.8	3.0	2.7	3.1
Semiwet	2.0	3.5	1.8	1.3	1.0	0.3
Mean	2.3	3.5	2.3	2.2	1.9	1.7
<i>Reduction (%) in yield</i>						
	18	0	35	57	62	91
<i>Subsoil moisture contribution (%)</i>						
	21	32	41	57	61	
^a CD at 5%	Season 0.4		Genotypes 0.3		Interaction 0.4	

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DISEASE RESISTANCE

Scented rices with stem rot (SR) and bacterial blight (BB) resistance

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SR, caused by *Sclerotium oryzae*, and BB, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, reduce rice yields in Haryana. We evaluated 68 scented rices for their reaction to these diseases at HAURRS in 1983-84 and 1984-85.

To screen for BB resistance, each entry was planted in 2-m rows at 20 × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with a BB suspension 21 d after transplanting (DT) for kresek and 45 DT for leaf blight and rated for resistance using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

SR screening was in field and laboratory. In the laboratory, cut stem

pieces were wound-inoculated with a small piece of agar-cultured *S. oryzae*. Inoculated stems were kept standing in a test tube rack in a tray with 2.5 cm of water. They were covered with plastic bags to maintain high humidity and were incubated at 28-30°C. Lesion length was measured 10 d after inoculation. Entries with lesions less than 10 mm long were considered resistant; those with 10-30 mm lesions, moderately resistant; and those with lesions more than 30 mm long, susceptible.

HKR220 was resistant to SR in laboratory tests in both seasons. HKR216 and HKR219 were resistant in the field. Pak basmati and RPSC 136 were SK resistant in all tests. They are a good source of SR resistance for breeding purposes.

Pak basmati also was moderately resistant at the kresek phase of BB.

RP2144-108-5-3-2 and NDR 601 also had moderate resistance to kresek. However, none of the materials were resistant to both BB phases. *ℒ*

Rice seedling resistance to brown spot (BS)

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We tested 15 rice varieties for seedling resistance to isolates of *Bipolaris oryzae* the BS fungus. In the greenhouse, 23-d-old seedlings were artificially inoculated with 3 isolates using a spore concentration of 3×10^4 spores/ml. Disease was measured on the 3d fully expanded leaf as lesion number per cm² and lesion size (mm²), and percent diseased leaf area was calculated.

The varieties had from 0.6-2.0 lesions/cm² and lesion size varied from 1.6 to 3.6 mm² (Fig. 1). Diseased leaf area ranged from 10.2 to 63.6% (Fig. 2). Tetep was resistant to three isolates. DR82 and IR42 produced the same lesion number and almost the same lesion size. IR36 was susceptible. Although there was some isolate-by-variety interaction, it was not sufficiently distinct to constitute evidence of physiological races of the BS fungus. *S*

1. Mean lesion number and mean lesion size on 15 rice varieties inoculated with 3 isolates of *Bipolaris oryzae* at seedling stage. IRRRI, 1985.

2. Mean diseased leaf area percentage recorded on 15 rice varieties inoculated with 3 isolates of *Bipolaris oryzae* at seedling stage. IRRRI, 1985.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) growth and development on rices with monogenic or digenic resistance

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Monogenic rice cultivars with genes *Wbph 1*, *Wbph 2*, *Wbph 3*, *Wbph 4*, and *Wbph 5* for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* and digenic cultivars with genes *Wbph 1 + Wbph 2*, *Wbph 1 + Wbph 3*, *Wbph 1 + 1* unidentified recessive gene, and *Wbph 2 + 1* unidentified recessive gene were tested for their effect on WBPH growth and development. Theoretically, rice cultivars with more than one gene for resistance are more resistant than those with only one gene.

Six-day-old seedlings of the test varieties were transplanted in 5-cm-diam clay pots at 1 seedling/pot. There were 10 replications with 3 pots/replication. The pots were set in standing water on a galvanized iron tray in the greenhouse and arranged in a randomized complete block design.

Two weeks after transplanting, potted plants were placed in mylar film cages.

Two newly hatched WBPH nymphs reared on TN1 were placed in each cage. As adults emerged, they were counted and the date was recorded. Individual adults were placed in plastic vials and weighed in an electric Mettler balance (1 µg sensitivity). When emergence was complete, percent survival, mean development time, and growth index and weight per adult were computed.

$$\% \text{ survival} = \frac{\text{no. of adults that emerged}}{\text{no. of nymphs used for infesting}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Growth index} = \frac{\% \text{ survival}}{\text{mean development period (d)}}$$

To determine WBPH population growth on the cultivars, 6-d-old seedlings were transplanted in 10-cm-diam clay pots at 5 seedlings/pot. There were 10 replications with one pot as one replication.

Two weeks after transplanting, the plants in each pot were placed in a 10×90-cm mylar film cage to exclude other rice pests and natural enemies. Ten days later, the plants were examined, pests and predators were removed, and 5 pair of 3-d-old WBPH adults were placed in

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